

A Study of consumer perception and product form

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Abstract

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Introduction

Branding is a strategic approach that enables the differentiation of a range of products and adds value to them. A successful brand builds a positive concept in consumers' minds and creates emotional associations between consumers and products. Brand identity serves to provide the purpose and meaning of a brand. It shows consumers what the brand offers and what it stands for. Brand identities are conveyed to consumers through advertisements, web pages, products and services. These means of communication create a unique brand image that results in a mixture of rational, sensual and emotional experiences.

Product form is one of the essential elements of a product that contributes to its brand image by conveying the visual identity of the brand. This paper reports an investigation that explored consumers' perceptions of product forms, and applied the identified perceptions of forms to inform the design of new products that convey specific aspects of a brand identity. The investigation was carried out through a case study using shampoo and conditioner bottles.

The Strategic use of product form for branding

In the context of branding, product form is an extrinsic attribute of a brand and a symbol of its identity. It contributes to three specific aspects of a brand identity: (1) brand recognition; (2) product differentiation; and (3) the creation of emotional associations with a branded product (Chen, 2005; Giard, 2005; Travis, 2000).

The contoured Coca-Cola bottle, Figure 1, for example, can be recognised all over the world. It speaks the language of the brand and presents the brand image. Coca-Cola was the first company that registered its contoured bottle as a trademark. Brand recognition also applies to ranges of products. The design of Dove soap bar, Dove cream wash bottle and the new bottles for Dove shampoo and conditioner, for example, all use two curved surfaces which provide a similar image that can be easily recognised and related to the brand, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: The Coca-Cola bottle

Figure 2: (a) Dove soap bar; (b) Dove cream wash bottle; (c) New Dove bottles

Product differentiation requires a product to deliver a distinctive brand image, of which product form is often a part, that is perceived by consumers as different from other products. For example, the Toilet Duck, Figure 3, introduced a plastic bottle with a duck-neck-shaped curve. This distinctive shape has successfully promoted the product to a leading position in its market segment.

Figure 3: The Toilet Duck bottle

In the automotive industry, cars are often characterised by strong emotional connections between consumers and products. Geometric form is one of the design elements that has been used to create an emotional link between products and consumers. The form of a car and its elements can be used to represent a personality and lifestyle that influence consumers' purchasing decisions. For example, the New Beetle creates a simple and elegant appearance by using arcs and circles as dominant features, Figure 4. The new shape is an interpretation of the original Beetle which combines the warm fuzzy feelings of the old design with the new model. This design strategy attracts customers from the 1950s to 1960s who have memories of the original Beetle (DeLorenzo, 1998). At the same time, the geometric shape of the new vehicle is a representation of kinetic and aesthetics. The body and the side windows fit into the top part of a golden ellipse; the front and back views are symmetrical and fit into a square; the logo on both views is near the centre point of the square; apart from wheels and fenders, circles appear in other small details, such as lights and car handles. The new appearance, together with new interior design, delivers an evolutionary design that meets the needs of a new generation customers.

Figure 4: The New Beetle

A case study using shampoo and conditioner bottles

The case study reported in this paper embraced the three aspects of a brand into a design consideration. It was used to explore the emotional impact of product forms on consumers, identify elements of product forms that influence consumers' emotional responses, and inform the emotional values to the design of new product shapes that deliver the three aspects of brand identity.

The case study used shampoo and conditioner bottles as sample products. Eighteen branded products found commonly in English supermarkets were selected to represent the product category. Bottles were selected from the 200ml-250ml range and are shown in Table 1. It can be seen that shapes in the sample covered a wide range of variants including linear and curvilinear shape elements, and both symmetric and asymmetric shapes.

Table 1: The 18 sample bottles

SP1	SP2	SP3	SP4	SP5	SP6
SP7	SP8	SP9	SP10	SP11	SP12
SP13	SP14	SP15	SP16	SP17	SP18

The case study was carried out using the following steps:

- Step 1 identified consumers' perceptions of bottle shapes;
- Step 2 defined sample bottles' shape characteristics and constructional principles;
- Step 3 observed consumers' perceptions and bottle shapes;
- Step 4 informed consumers' perceptions of bottle shapes to the generation of new bottle shapes;
- Step 5 Evaluated consumers' perceptions of new bottle shapes.

Step 1: Identification of consumers' perceptions

Semantic Differentiation survey

Consumers' perceptions of the bottle shapes were established through the use of a Semantic Differential survey. Semantic Differentiation is a technique that was developed for measuring meaning (Osgood et al., 1969). It measures differences between individuals' connotations of

words. Bipolar scales with contrasting adjectives at each end are used to plot the differences, for example:

Good ___: ___:___:___:___:___:___ Bad

For ease of data analysis, the technique includes three basic dimensions to correlate adjectives: **evaluation**, **potency**, and **activity** (EPA), such as good-bad for *evaluation*, strong-weak for *potency*, and active-passive for *activity* (Heise, 1970). In this study, the measurements of the EPA dimensions were used to create a three dimensional semantic space where the 18 sample bottles were plotted with respect to consumers' responses to the bottle shapes.

The main purpose for applying the Semantic Differentiation survey at this step is to explore consumers' perceptions of the 18 sample bottles and measure the difference in their reactions to different bottle shapes.

The survey was carried out by asking participants to score their responses according to six descriptive adjectives on a 7-point scale questionnaire. The six adjectives were *Smooth*, *Nourishing*, *Appealing*, *Professional*, *Natural*, and *Young*. Their selection was based on an analysis of information from three resources: (1) companies' websites, (2) a previous study on packages of body moisturisers conducted by students at the University of Leeds (Lewis et al., 2004), and (3) two papers reporting studies of hair treatment products (Ishihara et al., 1999; Ishihara et al., 2000). The six adjectives can be divided into two groups for two purposes. *Smooth*, *Nourishing*, and *Appealing* are three independent EPA dimensions. According to Lewis, et al. (2004), *Smooth* was classified as for **potency**, *Nourishing* for **activity**, and *Appealing* for **evaluation**. They were used to create a semantic space. Each sample occupies a different position on the semantic space. Their relative positions indicate the closeness between sample shapes as they were perceived by participants. *Professional*, *Natural*, and *Young* describe specific feelings that were used by companies to associate with their products. They were used in the survey to test whether they could be associated to certain bottle shapes. The survey was conducted in the Affective Research Laboratory of the School of Mechanical Engineering, the University of Leeds. Twenty female participants attended the survey. As the study focused on product form, participants were asked to concentrate on product shape and minimise the impact of sample colour.

Results of the survey

Data from the 20 questionnaires were collected and average scores for each adjective with regards to the 18 samples were calculated. The score range was set from 1 to 7. For each

sample, the higher a score, the more positive a reaction was gained on the adjective. For visualising and analysing the data, a three-dimensional EPA graph and a column graph were produced.

Figure 5 shows the EPA graph using adjectives *Smooth*, *Nourishing*, and *Appealing*. On the graph, scores for the three adjectives were used as coordinates to locate the position of each sample. Distances between pairs of samples were calculated using their coordinates in this space. In this case study, samples having a distance value of less than one were considered to be close which was taken to mean that they were perceived similarly. Four sample pairs, {SP4, SP5}, {SP7, SP8}, {SP13, SP14} and {SP15, SP16}, each pair from a same brand, were found to be close, circled in Figure 5. The other two pairs, {SP1, SP2} and {SP10, SP11}, were perceived very differently, linked by arrows in Figure 5. In addition, two samples from different brands, SP6 and SP17, were perceived similarly, which are circled by dotted lines in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The EPA graph for adjectives: *Appealing*, *Smooth* and *Nourishing*

Figure 6 shows the column graph for the other three adjectives, *Professional*, *Natural* and *Young*. It can be seen that samples with the top two scores for the adjective *Professional* were SP3 and SP9; the top two for *Young* were SP4 and SP5. Although the top two scores for

Natural were SP1 and SP18, they were not distinctly higher than the others. This indicates that adjectives *Professional* and *Young* had stronger associations with bottle shapes than the adjective *Natural*.

Figure 6: The column graph for adjectives: *Professional*, *Natural* and *Young*

Summary of findings

From the survey, three key findings were identified:

- (1) Four sample pairs, {SP4, SP5}, {SP7, SP8}, {SP13, SP14} and {SP15, SP16}, under a given brand were perceived as being similar. The other two pairs, {SP1, SP2} and {SP10, SP11} were perceived as being different. It can be seen that for brand recognition, some products have successfully delivered an image of a product family, while others are failed to create a consistency among products under the same brand.
- (2) Although samples SP6 and SP17 are from different brands, they were perceived similarly.
- (3) Samples, SP3 and SP9 were perceived as being professional-looking. This conformed to their brands that were advertised for professional use. Samples, SP4 and SP5, on the other hand, were marketed for children and they were perceived as being young-looking.

Discussion

The survey was carried out on 20 female participants using 18 sample bottles. Although participants' responses only represented a limited number of people's opinions, the results

served the purpose of this study. It showed that the 18 bottle shapes were scored differently in respect of a descriptive adjective, which implies that they were perceived differently by participants. Some perceptions of the bottle shapes were conformed with the specific aspects of a brand identity, for example, four sample pairs that each from a same brand were perceived similarly, two bottles were perceived as being professional-looking as they were advertised to their targeted consumers’.

It was noted that colour is an important factor for visual perception. Although participants were asked to focus only on the shapes of the samples, they expressed difficulty in avoiding the effect of colour, in particular SP18 was perceived as being *Natural* which was strongly influenced by its transparent bottle and fruity colour. To avoid distraction from colour, it was suggested that samples for future surveys should be painted in the same colour.

Step 2: Definition of bottles’ shape characteristics and constructional principles

The shapes of the 18 bottles were reverse engineered and their digital models were created using CAD/CAID tools, namely I-DEAS and Alias Design Studio. The process of generating digital models helped to explore the structure of the shapes and define constructional principle of bottle shapes. It was found that all 18 bottle shapes could be constructed by lofting along a set of cross sections. As such, the shape of each bottle in the collection of samples could be defined by its cross-sectional shapes and the spatial relations between these shapes.

The cross-sectional shapes of the 18 samples included ovals, circles, triangles, oblongs and octagons. Their spatial relations were defined by the relative positions of their defined points and the surfaces on which the cross-sectional shapes sat. The defined points could be aligned on either a straight or a curved line, shown as (a) and (b) in Table 2. The defined surfaces could be parallel or have an angle between them, shown as (c) and (d) in Table 2. The way in which these spatial relations could be used to define the bottle shapes in the sample is shown in Table 3.

Table 2: Spatial relations

Table 3: Bottle shapes defined using spatial relations

Based on the defined constructional principle, three criteria were identified to characterise the bottle shapes: symmetry, linearity, and cap-body continuity. The symmetry of each shape was determined by its two principle planes, xz and yz . For example, SP1 is symmetrical with respect to both xz and yz planes; SP4 is asymmetrical with respect to the yz plane and symmetrical to the xz plane; and SP15 is symmetrical with respect to the yz plane, but asymmetrical to the xz plane. Most of the bottles are asymmetrical with respect to the xz plane, so it was not considered in this study. Linearity describes the surfaces of a bottle. If a surface was constructed by lofting two cross-sectional shapes, it is a linear surface, such as SP3. If a surface was constructed by lofting more than two cross-sectional shapes, it is a curvilinear surface, such as SP1. Cap-body continuity describes the way in which a bottle cap is connected with its body. For example, SP10 has a shoulder between the cap and body, whereas the cap and body shape of SP1 are connected smoothly.

Step 3: Observations of consumers' perceptions and bottle shapes

Findings from the SD survey in Step 1 and shape characteristics and constructional principles defined in Step 2 have led to some observations that were used in Step 4 for the design of new product forms:

- (1) Results of the SD survey show that sample pairs {SP4, SP5}, {SP7, SP8}, {SP13, SP14} and {SP15, SP16} were perceived as being similar.

Table 4: Shape characteristics of sample pairs {SP4, SP5}, {SP7, SP8}, {SP13, SP14} and {SP15, SP16}

Samples	Symmetrical plane		Linearity	Cap-body continuity
	yz	xz		
SP4	Asymmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP5	Asymmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP7	Symmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines	Have a shoulder between cap and body
SP8	Asymmetric	Asymmetric	Curved body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP13	Symmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines with distinctive curves at the end of their body shapes	Have a shoulder between cap and body
SP14	Symmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines with distinctive curves at the end of their body shapes	Have a shoulder between cap and body
SP15	Symmetric	Asymmetric	Curved body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP16	Symmetric	Asymmetric	Curved body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly

From Table 4, it can be seen that, for sample pairs {SP4, SP5}, {SP13, SP14} and {SP15, SP16}, bottles of each pair have the same shape characteristics. In addition, {SP4, SP5} and {SP13, SP14} both have identical caps. The key features for recognising SP13 and SP14 are the distinctive curves at the end of their body shapes.

This led to **Observation 1** that bottles that were perceived similarly have same shape characteristics, identical caps or distinctive features.

An exception is bottle pair SP7 and SP8. They have very different geometric shapes. The reason for them to have been perceived similarly might be attributed to the strong Dove brand and participants' familiarity with the packaging. The discussions after the SD survey show that 15 out of 20 participants recognised SP7 and SP8 as from Dove.

(2) The other two pairs, {SP1, SP2} and {SP10, SP11} were perceived as being different.

Table 5: Shape characteristics of sample pairs {SP1, SP2} and {SP10, SP11}

Samples	Symmetrical plane		Linearity	Cap-body continuity
	yz	xz		
SP1	Symmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP2	Symmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines	Have a shoulder between cap and body
SP10	Symmetric	Symmetric	Linear body lines	Have a shoulder between cap and body
SP11	Symmetric	Symmetric	Linear body lines Oval shaped cap	Cap and body joined smoothly

From Table 5, it can be seen that the two bottle pairs that were perceived differently have inconsistency in their shape characteristics. The main difference between SP1 and SP2 is that the whole bottle shape of SP1 is joined by smooth curves, while SP2 has an obvious discontinued shoulder between body and cap. Similarly, SP10 has an obvious shoulder whereas the cap and body of SP11 are joined smoothly. In addition, SP10 is an angular shape with straight lines all around the bottle. Although SP11 has a angular body shape, its cap uses oval cross-sectional shapes.

(3) Although SP6 and SP17 are not from the same brand, they were perceived similarly.

Table 6: Shape characteristics of sample pairs {SP6, SP17}

Samples	Symmetrical plane		Linearity	Cap-body continuity
	yz	xz		
SP6	Symmetric	Symmetric	Linear body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP17	Symmetric	Symmetric	Curved body lines	Have a shoulder between cap and body

Table 6 shows that shape characteristics of SP6 and SP17 are different. Whereas, it was observed that their cross-sectional shapes are the same. This indicates that, in this case, cross-sectional shape makes a strong impression on consumers' visual perceptions.

This led to **Observation II** that bottles that were perceived similarly have the same cross-sectional shapes.

(4) SP3 and SP9 were perceived as being professional-looking

Table 7: Shape characteristics of sample pairs {SP3, SP9}

Samples	Symmetrical plane		Linearity	Cap-body continuity
	yz	xz		
SP3	Symmetric	Symmetric	Linear body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly
SP9	Symmetric	Asymmetric	Linear body lines	Cap and body joined smoothly

From Table 7, it can be seen that SP3 and SP9 both have linear body lines. The cross-sectional shape of SP3 is a circle where its width/height ratio equals to 1. For SP9, its cross-sectional shapes include a circle and an equilateral triangle where its width/height ratio equals to 1.15 which is approximate to 1.

This led to **Observation III** that the two bottles that were perceived as being professional-looking are linear designs with cross-sectional shapes having width/height ratio equaling to 1.

(5) SP4 and SP5 were perceived as being young-looking

From Table 4, it can be seen that SP4 and SP5 are both asymmetric from front view. They all have curved body lines. The cross-sectional shapes of SP4 and SP5 are similar, which all consist of irregular oval shapes.

This led to **Observation IV** that the two bottles that were perceived as being young-looking are asymmetrical with respect to the yz plane, and have curved body lines, and irregular cross-sectional shapes.

Step 4: Generation of new designs

The observations reported in Step 3 were used to inform the definition of a shape grammar¹ that was used to generate new bottle shapes. The observed emotional responses to specific product shapes were encoded in a collection of shape grammar rules. These rules were then used to derive new bottle shapes that conformed with the specified relationships. For example, **Observations I** and **II** were used to inform the generation of four family-looking bottles, A-D shown in Figure 7, which all have an identical curved surfaces on their caps, and their cross-section shapes are the same.

Shape grammar (Stiny, 1980) is a shape generating system that was originally developed for the analysis of architecture styles and the generation of designs that conform to a specific style. For reference on shape grammar and the application of shape grammars to designs, please refer to (Chen, 2005)

Figure 7: The new family bottles (from left: A, B, C and D)

Observation III was used to inform the generation of two professional-looking bottles, E and F shown in Figure 8, which are both linear, and their cross-section shapes all have the width/height ratio equaling to 1.

Figure 8: Two new professional-looking bottles (from left: E and F)

Step 5: Evaluation of new designs

Re-run Semantic Differential survey

The Semantic Differential survey described in Step 1 was re-run using new designs generated from Step 4. Four new bottles, B, D, E and F, were manufactured using an SLS rapid prototype machine. They were added to the original sample collection, while four original samples were removed from the sample group in order to maintain a sample total of 18.

Samples were re-ordered and numbered from SQ1 to SQ18. Table 8 shows the corresponded sample numbers between the two surveys.

Twenty-three female participants were recruited for the survey. None of them attended the SD survey in Step 1.

Table 8: Corresponded bottle numbers used in Phase I and III

Step 1	Step 5		Step 1	Step 5		Step 1	Step 5
SP11	SQ1		D	SQ7		SP13	SQ13
SP2	SQ2		SP15	SQ8		SP3	SQ14
SP6	SQ3		E	SQ9		SP5	SQ15
SP1	SQ4		SP8	SQ10		SP18	SQ16
SP10	SQ5		B	SQ11		SP14	SQ17
F	SQ6		SP7	SQ12		SP9	SQ18

The lesson learned from Step 1 was corrected in Step 5. In the re-run SD survey, all 18 samples were displayed in white in order to effectively test participants’ reactions to only the shape of samples.

Results of the re-run survey

Figure 9 shows a EPA graph of the three adjectives: *Nourishing*, *Smooth*, and *Appealing*. Among five sample pairs, three pairs have a distance value of less than 1: {SQ10, SQ12}, {SQ13, SQ17}, and {SQ7, SQ11}. The first two pairs repeated the result in Step 1. The third pair, {SQ7, SQ11}, are new designs for the product family.

Figure 9: The EPA graph for adjectives: *Appealing*, *Smooth* and *Nourishing* (Phase III)

Figure 10 shows a column graph of the three adjectives: *Professional*, *Natural*, and *Young*. It was found that new designs SQ6 and SQ9 were among bottle shapes that had high scores on *Professional*. This indicates that they were perceived as professional-looking.

Figure 10: The column graph for adjectives: *Professional*, *Natural* and *Young* (Phase III)

Discussion

The results showed that the two new bottles that have used **Observations I** and **II** in their design generations were perceived similarly and the two new bottles that have used **Observation III** in their design generations were perceived as professional-look.

Some of the results repeated findings from the survey in Step 1. For example, the two sample pairs that were used in the survey in Step 1 were perceived similarly. SQ15 which was SP5 in Step 1 was perceived as being young-looking. SQ18 which was SP9 in Step 1 was perceived as being professional-looking.

However, it was noticed that a number of bottles that were not recognised as being professional-looking in the Step 1 scored highly on the adjective *professional* in this survey. There are a number of factors that may have caused these discrepancies. In particular, the change colour of all samples to white could be one of the major cause.

Conclusion

The work reported in this paper highlighted the important role that a product form plays in the delivery of brand identities. Brand recognition, product differentiation, and creating emotional associations with a product are defined as key aspects that a product form delivers in conveying a branding strategy.

The case study using shampoo and conditioner bottles presented a research approach that embodied the three aspects into design considerations. By quantifying consumers' emotional associations with brands, consumers' perceptions of product geometric shapes were identified and used to inform the generation of new designs. This work underpins the development of toolkits that will enable product development teams to better understand their brand and the relationship between the brand and products.

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